

WOMEN, EMPOWERMENT AND AFFIRMATION STRATEGIES

INDRA KERTATI¹, SUPARNO² and SETYOHADI PRATOMO³

¹ Lecturer of Master of Public Administration, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, 17 Agustus 1945 University Semarang, Jl. Pawiyatan Luhur Bendan Duwur Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia.
Email: indra-kertati@untagsmg.ac.id

² Professor of Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, 17 Agustus 1945 University Semarang, Jl. Pawiyatan Luhur Bendan Duwur Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia. Email: suparno@untagsmg.ac.id

³ Lecturer of Public Administration, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, 17 Agustus 1945 University Semarang, Jl. Pawiyatan Luhur Bendan Duwur Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia,
Email: setyohadi_1505@untagsmg.ac.id

Abstract

Woman empowerment is the process of establishing women as social subjects who can rise and work due to their own abilities and the assistance of their surroundings. There have been efforts to empower women, but they have not generated significant outcomes. Indicators such as the Female Labor Force Participation Rate, the average duration of education, the contribution of women to family income, and the percentage of women who are still disenfranchised at the grassroots level demonstrate this. This research aims to reveal the woman empowerment, particularly impoverished and marginalized women. Descriptive qualitative research paired with secondary data is employed. A questionnaire with 175 samples, in-depth interviews, and Focus Group Discussions were utilized to collect data. The triangulation method, data source, and theory were employed for data analysis. The results of the study indicate that the local government's effort to empower women has not produced substantial effects. Empowerment still has not found a clear concept. For this reason, an affirmation approach is required, particularly how to build woman empowerment from within, as well as how to offer up places for involvement so that women in an undeveloped community no longer face impediments.

Keywords : empowerment, women, marginalization, vulnerability, poverty, affirmation, strategy

1. INTRODUCTION

The National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) identifies the empowerment of women and the protection of children as two of its most significant priorities. Specifically, the RPJMN identifies gender equality, woman empowerment, and protection as crucial aspects for women's meaningful participation in development. (Indonesian Ministry of National Development Planning, 2020).

Considering that the gender gap in many development domains is still very large and PUG institutions have been ineffective, this strategy was formulated. The GPI and IDG in 2018 only achieved 90.99 and 72.10, Indonesia's Gender Inequality Index is rated 104 out of 162 nations surveyed and is the third lowest country in ASEAN, and the female Labor Force Participation Rate (TPAK) has only reached 51.89 percent compared to 83.13 percent for men (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2019). On the other hand, women's participation in formal employment remains extremely low, at 34.22 percent compared to 65.78 percent for men.

The implementation of the PUG strategy faces numerous obstacles, such as the implementation of policies, analytical tools, and commitment and political support for gender equality, which

are not yet optimal, and a lack of understanding of gender concepts and issues, as well as the benefits of PUG in development, particularly in provinces, districts/cities, and villages. Low and not yet uniform, and institutional capability in implementing PUG, notably in terms of human resources and the supply and use of gender data at each stage of development, is inadequate (KPPPA 2020).

UN Women also reported that 740 million women worldwide are employed in the informal economy. They lost their formal economy employment. Women in the informal sector who have unpaid care obligations and are suffering economic recovery are unlikely to have access to social protection, leading in economic hardship such as increasing poverty, food insecurity, and depletion of assets and debt (Tina Jhonson 2021).

According to the Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 050-5889 for the Year 2021 Concerning the Results of Verification, Validation, and Inventory Updating of Classification, Codefication, and Nomenclature of Development Planning and Finance. Area, these various conditions encourage the government to provide sufficient space by allowing for a variety of alternative sub-activities. Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 050-5889 has not been able to satisfactorily address the issue of woman empowerment in the regions.

When women who reside in underprivileged and remote places are powerless, the matter becomes much more problematic. Women in rural regions are not only pushed aside and out of the informal sector, but they are also forced to move overseas or to cities in search of other employment opportunities. Unquestionably, they join the labor sector as housekeepers or unpaid employees.

Attempting to expose the powerlessness that results from restricted access, as well as the advantages of development that are out of reach, is the objective of constructing empowerment beginning with the most remote areas. This research intends to assess the empowerment of women and the responsibilities performed by the government and local governments in enhancing their capabilities, beginning with the most remote locations. This research is located in Grobogan Regency.

2. METHOD

This research employed a qualitative descriptive technique to examine the phenomena of woman empowerment in rural or inaccessible places (Nassaji 2015). This study also considers the role of the federal and local governments in enhancing the capabilities of women.

Through surveys, in-depth interviews, observations, and reading, data was collected. Women in the village received questionnaires. The local government gives this group empowerment status. As many as 175 individuals have responded to the survey. Local governments dealing with woman empowerment and child protection, as well as people in charge of woman empowerment and child protection, were the topic of in-depth interviews. The number of respondents in this survey was ten.

Exploring the Activity Plan papers of corporate executives who implement woman empowerment constitutes the literature review. The strategy of gathering data through literature is also intended to investigate several comparable studies that can be used as a reference for reviewing study outcomes.

Triangulation is used for data processing (David Chitate 2020). (1) Triangulation of methodologies, (2) triangulation of data sources, and (3) triangulation of theory constitute the triangulation model. Method triangulation is performed by comparing information or data collected in several methods. Triangulation is performed at this step if the data or information collected from the subject or study source is suspect (Torrance 2012).

Triangulation of data sources is the process of determining the veracity of certain information using many techniques and sources of data collection. In the form of an information formulation or thesis statement, triangulation theory is the end product of research. The material is then examined with appropriate theoretical viewpoints in order to eliminate the researcher's own bias in the resulting results or conclusions. In addition, theoretical triangulation can enhance comprehension depth (Matthew B. Miles 1994).

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Achievement Indicator

The Gender Development Index is an outcome measure of the ratio of female HDI to male HDI. The GPA value of 100 indicates that there is no gap between the human development achievements of men and women. A GPA value below 100 indicates that there is still a gap in the achievement of human development, namely the development of women is still below that of men. Vice versa, if the GPA is worth more than 100, it means that the development achievement of men is below that of women.

The IPG is formed from the components of health, education, and a decent life as well as the HDI. Life expectancy represents the health dimension, the expected length of schooling and the average length of schooling represent the knowledge dimension, and per capita expenditure represents the economic dimension presented by gender. The Grobogan Regency IPG development from 2017 to 2021 fluctuated and tended to increase, from 85.69 in 2017 to 86.14 in 2020, then in 2021 it fell to 85.89 with achievements below the national and provincial averages. This can be seen clearly in the following graph:

Figure 1: Development of the Gender Development Index (GDI) of Grobogan Regency, Central Java Province and National Year 2017-2021

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics of Central Java, 2022

The relative position of Grobogan Regency in 2021 is 85.89, below the Central Java Province (92.48) and National (91.27) and occupies the second lowest position after Blora Regency at 84.59. Compared to the surrounding districts, Grobogan Regency's IPG position is above Blora Regency but below Rembang, Jepara, Pati and Kudus districts. This position also places Grobogan Regency at number 34 in Central Java. The issue of the position of Grobogan Regency at number 34 is not an easy thing. The hard efforts made, in fact, have not been comparable to reaching the gender gap problem that occurs. The picture below shows the relative position of Grobogan Regency IPG with its hinterland.

Figure 2. The Relative Position of the Gender Development Index (GDI) of Grobogan Regency in 2021

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics of Central Java, 2022

Specifically, Grobogan Regency's low GPI can be seen from its constituent composition, namely life expectancy representing the health dimension, the expected length of schooling and the average length of schooling representing the knowledge dimension, and per capita expenditure representing the economic dimension. Life Expectancy Age (LEA) by sex from 2017 to 2021 shows an increase but the LEA of men is lower than the LEA of women. In 2021 the UHH for women is 76.66 years old and the LEA for men is 73, 00 years.

The low male LEA was analyzed by a number of specialists. Seifarth JE, McGowan CL, Milne KJ. (2012); Luy M, Minagawa Y. (2014) Male fetuses are biologically weaker and more susceptible to maternal stress and complicated pregnancies than female fetuses, as demonstrated by Eriksson JG, Kajantie E, Osmond C, et al. (2010), Glover V. (2016), and Marais GAB, Gaillard J, Vieira C, et al. (2012), as cited by Hossin M. This is evident in the greater incidence of preterm and neonatal births and infant death among boys compared to girls. On the basis of sex differences at birth, it is commonly believed that hereditary abnormalities are responsible for men's excessive mortality. Estrogen is protective against cardiovascular disease and contributes to the reduced prevalence of menstrual stoppage. Androgens, which are more prevalent in men, are connected with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. A female immune system that is more robust is an additional aspect that might contribute to the lifespan disparity. The female body is known to produce a more robust immune response and more antibodies than the male body (Hossin 2021).

In Grobogan Regency, gender-based expectations for the number of years spent in education (Average Expected Length of School/AELS), increased across the board. Men dominate the HLS in 2021, with an average age of 13.77 years compared to 12.44 years for women. In the meanwhile, the average length of schooling by gender will increase in 2021 compared to 2020. The average age of men with AELS is 9.27 years, compared to 8.86 years for women. The short duration of education is due to women's tardiness in enrolling in school. According to the the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, the digital literacy index assessed by four pillars — digital culture, digital ethics, digital skills, and digital safety — indicates that women continue to lag far behind men. " The composite index of digital literacy, which is calculated from the 4 pillars of culture, ethics, skills, and safety, reveals that women continue to lag far behind men in all 4 categories.

Grobogan regency-adjusted per capita expenditures by sex each increased in 2017 to 2021. In 2021, male per capita expenditure was Rp. 15,450 higher than female per capita expenditure was Rp. 7,504. Although there is an increase, when viewed from the per capita expenditure figures, it is included in the low category. Surprisingly in the formal sector itself, the female workforce participation rate is no more than 38.63%, far behind by men who reached 46.29% in 2018. This has an impact on inequality in the female workforce, which does not reflect the number of female workers in the formal sector being absorbed. Many women prefer to work in the informal sector, namely jobs that do not take a lot of time, such as formal sector workers whose working hours are denser (Reyhan Farqi Wasista 2020).

Another important indicator is the Gender Empowerment Index (GEM), which shows the extent of women's active role in economic and political life. The active role of women in economic and political life includes political participation, economic participation and decision-making as well as control of economic resources, which is referred to as the IDG dimension. The development of IDG in 2017 to 2021 continues to fluctuate and tends to increase, namely in 2017 it was 56.01 increasing to 63.70 in 2018, then in 2019 it decreased to 56.31, in 2020 it rose to 57.18 and in 2021 to 58.03. This condition is not relevant to the development of the Central Java Provincial GEM, which decreases every year and the National GEM increases every year. More details can be seen in the following image:

Figure 3: Development of the Gender Empowerment Index (IDG) of Grobogan Regency, Central Java Province and National Year 2017-2021

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics of Central Java, 2022

Grobogan Regency's GEM achievement in 2021 is 58.03, below the Central Java Province's 71.64 and National's 76.26 and compared to the surrounding districts, Grobogan Regency occupies the second lowest position after Jepara Regency which is 56.66. If you look at the composition, the involvement of women in Grobogan Regency from 2017 to 2021 shows a stagnation of 12% every year. This condition is relevant to increasing national and declining provinces. The involvement of women in the Grobogan Regency parliament in 2021 by 12% is in the 3rd lowest position from the surrounding districts after Kudus Regency (8.89%) and Blora Regency (11.11%). The involvement of women in the Grobogan district parliament is still below the national average of 21.89% and above the provincial average of 18.33%.

The achievement of the indicator of women as professionals in Grobogan Regency in 2017 to 2021 shows an increase, from 43.28% to 51.39% being in the highest position from the surrounding districts, namely Pati, Blora, Kudus and above the average provincial and national. The achievement of the indicator of Women's Income Contribution in Grobogan district from 2017 to 2021 shows an increase every year. In 2017 it was 24.80% and in 2021 it was 25.85%. This condition places the 2nd lowest position after Jepara Regency (24.08%) from the surrounding districts. And below the provincial and national average.

3.2. Woman empowerment

Woman empowerment is a common definition of woman empowerment. This need outside assistance to strengthen the subject, mainly women. In many instances, empowerment signifies improvement from a bad circumstance to a better one. This indicates that empowerment has a broad scope, yet the subject remains the empowerment's target.

Development of woman empowerment is the process by which women obtain the capacity to make strategic life decisions in the setting of once denied skills. There are three interconnected aspects of woman empowerment that are essential: resources, agency, and accomplishment (Huis et al. 2017a).

Resources refer to monetary, human, and societal expectations and allocations, whereas agency is the capacity or perception of capacity to choose one's objectives, act on those goals, and set one's goals as a result of one's own life. Among the accomplishments are outcomes ranging from increased welfare to equal participation of women in politics.

The fundamental idea is that woman empowerment is the act of acquiring and utilizing resources inside an organization to accomplish particular goals. In its implementation, the dimensions of woman empowerment include significant dimensions, such as the personal dimension, which includes a place of control, self-confidence, self-esteem, and self-efficacy; the relationship dimensions, which include domestic violence, bargaining power, freedom of mobility, size of social networks, social capital, and collective action involvement; and the social dimensions, which include the percentage of female microfinance borrowers, the percentage of female borrowers with a higher education, and the percentage of female borrowers with (Huis et al. 2017a).

Considering the three dimensions of woman empowerment, it seems impossible to make it happen. This condition can be shown from the data that efforts to empower women in local government activities there are 33.32 percent of activities carried out in 2018, then 33.33 percent were carried out in 2019 and the rest were carried out in 2020. Compared to other field activities, it turns out that this portion not yet fully cover women in an area, especially vulnerable women in the periphery. This amount is not specifically given to women.

Based on these dimensions, the coverage that can be achieved that most women who are on the edge have only reached a few dimensions and coverage. This problem is increasingly emerging considering that women who are marginalized are those who experience the vulnerability of education, work, and business. The number of poor people in Grobogan Regency continues to increase. The Central Bureau of Statistics report states that the number of poor people in 2019 was 161,900 people, increasing in 2020 by 172,250 people and in 2021 to 175,720 people (BPS, 2022 (<https://grobogankab.bps.go.id/indicator/23/150/1/sum-population-poor.html>)). The number has not been disaggregated by gender.

The Central Bureau of Statistics released the percentage of the population living below the poverty line in 2018-2021 showing that women have a higher number than men. Even within

four years the number of women living below the poverty line has increased, while the number of men has decreased (BPS 2022). More details can be seen in the following table:

Table 1: Percentage of Population Living Below the National Poverty Line Gender (percent)

Gender	Percentage of Population Living Below the National Poverty Line Gender (percent)			
	2018	2019	2020	2021
Male	9,59	9,18	10,16	9,92
Female	10,06	9,63	10,22	10,37

Source Url: <https://www.bps.go.id/indicator/23/1538/1/persentase-penduduk-yang-hidup-di-bawah-garis-kemiskinan-nasional-menurut-jenis-kelamin.html>

If the data is applied in Grobogan Regency, it is estimated that women under the poverty line will reach 89,809 people while men are 85,911 people, while the community empowerment program only involves 30% of women. Therefore, if community empowerment programs and activities are only 33% of the total programs and activities in one district, then women only get very small development results.

Taking into account the three dimensions mentioned above, it turns out that not all of these dimensions can be enjoyed by women who are below the poverty line. Grobogan Regency with 273 villages mapped as Independent Villages with 4 villages, 29 developed villages, 223 developing villages and 17 underdeveloped villages, it is certain that women's access and control in enjoying the results of development are still far from expectations.

Table 2: Dimensions of Woman empowerment

Dimension	Variable	Performance Achievement
Personal	control place	Belum semua tercapai
	self-confidence	Not all achieved.
	pride	Achieved.
	self-efficacy	Not all achieved.
Relation	domestic violence	There is still a lot going on, especially women in underdeveloped villages.
	bargaining power	Not yet fully owned, dependence on men is still high, patriarchal culture is still strong.
	mobility freedom	Limited, but for women in urban areas, accessibility is affordable.
	social network size	Limited to women in disadvantaged areas, but in urban areas more and more are able to access.
	social capital	Big enough in the form of cooperation.
Social Dimension	collective action engagement	Large enough, limited to the environment in the community itself.
	female microfinance borrower	Some were absorbed in loans from Cooperatives, Dasa Wisma, PKK whose managers were women.
	female borrowing with school-age children at school	Some of the poor depend on loans to cover their children's schooling needs.
	women's leadership in MFIs	Not many found
	Promotion and reduction of female staff	Not many found
Average loan balance for female borrowers	Micro and small size	

Source: The results of the qualitative analysis by the researcher are based on the Huis, M, Hansen N Concept.

On the grounds of the results of the study based on the aforementioned aspects, it can be stated that marginalized and peripheral women are still a long way from being empowered or empowering themselves. Numerous contributing elements include the availability of knowledge, amenities, and infrastructure, as well as poverty and isolation. Women in rural and distant locations have power over social capital and participation in collective action. In specific cases, such as community work, assisting neighbors in need, and assisting neighbors who marry or circumcise their children, social capital and participation in collective action only rely on the strength of mutual cooperation. This skill is restricted to a tiny community within the village.

The intriguing aspect of this discovery is that patriarchal society is still prevalent in both rural and urban places, including both independently developed and distant communities. This paternalistic paradigm is exemplified not just by submission to men in religious matters, but also in the realm of decision-making (Irawanto and Ramsey 2011). Paternalism is the practice of restricting the freedom of an individual or group for their own benefit. Paternalism implies that a person acts against his own choice or that his action demonstrates an attitude of superiority. The terms paternalistic and paternalist are typically employed with derogatory or disparaging connotation. The following idea movement is egalitarian with a major topic, namely Men for Equity, which defines the division of roles and concerns of men in relation to women's issues (Estevan-Reina, de Lemus, and Megas, 2020). However, this tendency was not observed in our investigation. The findings actually result in women and children submitting to male family leaders.

Paternalism among indigenous Indonesians, particularly the Javanese, is extensively documented. The Javanese have historically assigned the male component the responsibility to rule and govern within the context of the family and community. Dominance is founded on the fatherism ideals that depict the patronage between the paternal (father) and the mother (wife and child). Bapakism is awakened in the father as the head of the family in order for him to wield high-level power paired with moral ideals that the wife and children are supposed to obey (Irawanto and Ramsey 2011).

3.3. Woman Empowerment Pattern

Woman empowerment takes numerous forms. The used patterns are distinct from one another. This is owing to the fact that urban and rural regions have distinct histories. Gender and Development has replaced the Women in Development paradigm about woman empowerment. In the previous paradigm, woman empowerment made women the object of development; but, in the current paradigm, women are the subject of development. In spite of this, woman empowerment is still viewed as a separate enterprise from child protection. If this becomes a special case, the fundamental challenge will be that the scope and authority will be restricted.

Decree of the Ministry of Home Affairs No. 90 of 2019, which was developed in accordance with Decree of the Ministry of Home Affairs No. 050-5889 of 2021 (Decree of the Ministry of Home Affairs, 2019), locks the position of overseeing woman empowerment and child

protection based on the authority and responsibilities of the service. In the meanwhile, not all other affairs supervisors see the gender viewpoint to be mainstreaming in development.

Domestic Government Regulation No. 90 of 2019, which was developed as, stipulated in Kepmdagri 050-5889 of 2021 (Kemendagri 2019) places the position of overseeing woman empowerment and child protection in a locked position according to the authority and affairs that are the responsibility of the service. Meanwhile, other affairs supervisors have not all viewed the gender perspective as mainstreaming in development. The results of the study show that the target groups in Grobogan Regency community empowerment programs and activities have tended to be intended for the general public (21 percent) and vulnerable community groups (21 percent), for children 12 percent, women 16 percent, teenagers 12 percent. , 10 percent for the elderly and 8 percent for the disabled. Woman empowerment only gets a small portion, namely 16 percent and the supervisors of woman empowerment and child protection, namely the Office of Woman empowerment, Child Protection and Family Planning, Community Empowerment Office, Health Office and Education Office, handle most of it.

The full picture can be seen in the following graph:

Figure 4: Percentage of Targets of Community Empowerment Programs and Activities in Grobogan Regency

The pattern of community empowerment is carried out with various models, most of which are technical assistance such as capacity and skill development, business equipment assistance, education assistance, facilitation for repairing uninhabitable houses, health assistance, socialization, dissemination and mentoring. This pattern refers to two things, namely the Community Empowerment Process Model and the Community Empowerment Model itself (Widjajanti 2011). The first pattern is characterized by the ability of the community to analyze problems, plan, implement and evaluate an empowerment program; this means that it requires analytical skills and abilities. The second pattern is to strengthen the role of human capital and

physical capital. The pattern of woman empowerment from the results of this study shows three patterns, namely:

1. Capacity Building Pattern, namely the OPD in charge of affairs determines the sub-activities of socialization, training, and dissemination. The resulting output increases the knowledge of the target group. This pattern is not fully capable of empowering the community.
2. Assistance pattern, namely the supervisors of development affairs who facilitate both technical and non-technical assistance. Assistance can be in the form of technical assistance, equipment assistance or financial assistance. This pattern can be directly felt by the target group, but the level of sustainability is low.
3. Empowerment Patterns are patterns that are built through a long process. This pattern is commonly used by NGOs in collaboration with local government agencies. Dinas provide funding, NGOs work in the field. Although expensive, this policy combines increasing public understanding, skills as well as strengthening the target group's institutions. This pattern is not only expensive but also takes a long time. This is something that is often discussed between agencies when it comes to using this third pattern.

3.4. Women Empowerment Strategy

Woman empowerment is described as the process through which women develop the capacity to make strategic life decisions within the framework of hitherto unattainable skills (Kabeer 1999). Other study indicates that empowerment is a process that enables people to take action and raise concerns that are vital to their lives, communities, and society. This notion stresses the increase of women's unique capabilities and their freedom to select what they desire and anticipate. This definition is also a choice that is highly dependent on a person's ability to pick what is best for himself (Cattaneo and Chapman 2010). This viewpoint is not a reflection on modernity or the freedom to achieve what is anticipated; rather, it is an effort by women to develop their abilities.

Women's individual choices are historically and structurally conditioned by women based on reality rather than an emphasis on individual freedom and growth, which might marginalize women's experiences in different communities, according to previous study (Budgeon). 2015). The study's findings reveal a similar pattern: traditional women face challenges while deciding to make positive changes to their life, but they also collide with the environmental conditions in which they reside, such as poverty, vulnerability, insecurity, and limited capability. When presented with the option to be empowered, they have the courage to emerge from the shadows of their existence and make the decision to rise up and become empowered.

Decolonial feminist psychology studies stress the importance of being sensitive to cultural contexts and gaining insight from the experiences of women in low-income countries who are able to create spaces that reflect their capacity to develop in accordance with the values they hold and believe (Dutt, Grabe, and Castro, 2016). Even if in a different temporal dimension, the values accepted from a social perspective have demonstrated astonishing scalability due to the emergence and creation of new ideas to escape the surrounding environment. This study

also demonstrates that mothers living in precarious, impoverished, and rural settings integrate their thoughts into their values and transmit modifications to their kids. This state is evident from the shift in values towards autonomy. Women who have inherited new beliefs on empowerment know that woman empowerment must be followed by self-sufficiency through improved education.

In accordance with this viewpoint, a recent research focused on the notion of woman empowerment through communal as opposed to individual company ownership (Dutt et al. 2016). This study demonstrates the same, although the empowerment of this model is more determined by the government or by woman empowerment than by women's initiative. This may be shown by comparing the number of Joint Business Groups (KUBE) created to the number of existing groups; the success rate has not been proportional to the number of existing groups. Some have been proven to be effective when begun by women themselves. Those who participate in joint ventures adhere to cultural norms that prioritize group progress above individual development (Kurtiş and Adams, 2015).

Collectively, woman empowerment depicts empowerment as a multi-asset notion comprising several components ranging from women's comprehension of the causes of their oppression to communal action toward social change. This study is based on the premise that involvement in small groups with a shared objective is the first step towards empowering women. Individual and communal agency are therefore essential to the empowerment of women (Dutt et al. 2016).

It is difficult to strengthen woman empowerment in situations of vulnerability, poor development accessibility, and limited decision-making. Women in precarious positions and surroundings, coupled with a pervasive patriarchal society, isolate themselves and limit their interaction with others in their area. Therefore, a unique strategy is required for the success of these endeavors. This method involves a partnership of several aspects, including resources, agency, and success. Material, human, and societal expectations and allocations are examples of resources. The capacity or perception of ability to identify one's objectives, act on those goals, and determine one's goals as a result of one's own strategic activities constitutes agency. Achievements span from enhancing social welfare to establishing gender parity in politics. The fundamental idea is that woman empowerment is the process of acquiring and utilizing resources inside an organization to achieve certain goals (Kabeer 1999).

The results of the study indicate that to strengthen woman empowerment, the option they anticipate is a procedure that enables women to act and address problems that are vital to the lives of people, communities, and society as a whole. Consequently, the notions of capacity building, agency, and outcomes are encompassed within the dimensions that raise their social standing.

This three-dimensional model of woman empowerment includes (1) personal empowerment, which refers to personal beliefs and actions; (2) relational empowerment, which refers to beliefs and actions related to relevant others; and (3) community empowerment, which refers to the situation of women in the larger context of society in order to understand how woman empowerment can develop (Huis et al. 2017b). These three dimensions are interdependent and

cannot be separated. In the context of individual empowerment, women must voice their own difficulties, so why not grow individually?

The study's results revealed unexpected discoveries. A lack of education and the inability to overcome family difficulties, such as the incapacity to protect themselves and their families, marital abuse, and a sense of inferiority to enter a society with a higher individual standing, typically accompany poor women. Individual empowerment must be performed directly in order to comprehend the individual's potential and willingness to progress. Taking this into consideration, empowering women is a lengthy process.

This model allows for a more dynamic understanding of why some women may feel more empowered than others, why some women can express higher levels of personal empowerment but not relational empowerment, and why one intervention had a positive impact on woman empowerment in one area but not another.

Integrating all three characteristics of woman empowerment into a single study model gives fresh theoretical insights into how woman empowerment might evolve through more open access to services, as well as obvious practical implications for field players.

The results of the study indicate that the approach implemented by local governments is still a one-way strategy that has not satisfied the requirements of women in relation to local governments' development aspirations. The empowerment process should result in women having the autonomy to pursue their own life objectives. Power is crucial (Gutiérrez, 1991; Kar et al., 1999; Masterson & Owen, 2006; Speer & Hughey, 1995), since it is the topic of a social interaction that is not restricted to the battle for supremacy but encompasses the different ways in which individuals exercise influence (Kato and Kratzer 2013).

Therefore, a gain in power corresponds to a rise in a person's influence in social interactions with every other human being. Empowerment as an interaction in which a person who lacks the ability to set a personally meaningful goal is oriented toward increasing strength, takes action toward the goal, observes and reflects on the impact of the action, and develops self-efficacy, knowledge, and competence pertaining to his existence is defined.

The primary method for empowering vulnerable, impoverished women and family heads who lack access to development is to provide them room to stand up and work on talents that are backed by capacity and sponsored by the government or community developers. Another technique that may be utilized is the adaptation strategy, which involves testing the proposed intervention beforehand. This method is time-consuming. This process of adaptation aims to guarantee that the target is able to think critically about the experiment and uncover its potential. The achievement of woman empowerment may be achieved via the employment of these two tactics, provided that all parties are willing and willing to participate.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that efforts to increase woman empowerment follow the following patterns: (1) capacity building that is not fully capable of empowering the

community; (2) the pattern of assistance, which consists of facilitating technical and non-technical assistance to the target group; and (3) the pattern of empowerment is a pattern that is constructed through a lengthy process involving the cooperation of the parties. In order to attain woman empowerment, it is necessary to provide room for women to be creative, develop their potential, and remove obstacles that have hindered them. The adaption method can be implemented as a government pilot project in collaboration with NGOs, colleges, and even entrepreneurs in order to enhance the welfare of women.

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